

VALUE4FARM

D7.2 Data Management Plan

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Nature of the Deliverable		
R	Document, report	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	X

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open and automatically posted online	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grand Agreement	
CI	Classified information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	
	Classified information: CONFIDENTIAL UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)	
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AU	Aarhus Universitët
CIB	Consorzio Italiano Biogas e Gassificazione
EIHP	Energetski Institut Hrvoje Pozar
EQY	Euroquality
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DST	Decision Support Tool
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
INA	INAGRO
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IUNG	Instytut Uprawy Nawożenia I Gleboznawstwa, Panstwowy Instytut Badawczy
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MITIS	MITIS
OKD	Orkidea Samstarfsverkefni
REM	REM TEC S.R.L.
UCSC	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore
UFZ	Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GMBH
UREAD	University of Reading
V4F	VALUE4FARM
WBA	World Biogas Association
WP	Work Package
WU	Wageningen University

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KEYWORDS LIST

- Data Management Plan
- Open Science
- FAIR principles
- GDPR

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Value4Farm project aims to demonstrate the effectiveness, sustainability and replicability of three renewable-based local value chains coupling sustainable food production and renewable-energy production with the aim of contributing to the defossilisation of the agricultural sector by matching local needs in terms of electricity, heat, mobility, residual bioresources and land management.

The present deliverable sets out the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Value4Farm project, on the management, exploitation, accessibility and preservation measures of the generated data and practices to ensure Open Science.

During the course of the project, a great quantity of data will be generated on renewable energy technologies in agriculture by literature studies, pilots and demonstrations, sustainability assessments, surveys, ... Experimental and research data such as specifications (WP1), outcomes of the crop protocols (WP2), all data from the demonstrations (WP3), useful data for the sustainability assessment and Decision Support Tool (DST) (WP4), data generated of the replication sites (WP5), etc. will be collected/generated in Value4Farm, and used by partners to prepare the deliverables, follow the KPIs and the progress made in the project. The generated data will follow the FAIR (findability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability) principles. Furthermore, the project will collect information reflecting the needs of relevant stakeholders and in particular farmers, as well as their personal data (e.g. contact data). These kind of data will be handled according to the General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679/EU). Privacy and confidentiality will be protected by following ethical guidelines, as well as the collection of informed consent.

In order to guarantee a good Data Management, Value4Farm will also provide recommendations and support guidelines to partners on how to collect, generate, manage and re-use the Value4Farm data. This DMP specifies how research will be conducted and how data will be collected, processed, monitored, catalogued, and disseminated during the project lifetime, as well as after the end of the project.

As this is a living document, regular updates will be made and reported.

1. INTRODUCTION

To comply with Horizon Europe requirements, a data management plan (DMP) describes which data the Value4Farm project expects to acquire or generate during the course of the project and how these data will be managed. This plan contains all rules with regard to the management of data and is validated by all partners. If needed, monitoring and adjustment will be made every six months, by progressing insights or whenever significant changes arise. A first version of this DMP is given in the following.

2. DATA SUMMARY

To achieve the goals set in the project, seven Work Packages (WPs) will enable the partners to execute the planned activities in a logical and interconnected way (Figure 1). Data will mainly be collected and WP1, WP2 and WP5. Additionally, new data will mainly be generated in WP3 and WP4.

Figure 1: Project Work Package Structure

2.1. DATA TYPES, FORMAT, SIZE AND STORAGE

The types of data generated in Value4Farm include both qualitative and quantitative data, primary and secondary. It includes the collection of innovative knowledge, best practices and other publicly available data on renewable energy technologies in agriculture, the results of the workshops and international conferences, data generated by questionnaires, evaluation data on bottlenecks and barriers on the implementation of new technologies and best practices (e.g. data on cost-benefit analysis and regulatory aspects), ... Value4Farm will only generate and collect open data which is free to access, reuse, repurpose and redistribute. Protected sensitive research data will be managed according to a dedicated Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Management Plan via a dedicated task (T5.3).

Table 1 gives a generalized overview of data types used in the project. Working draft documents and confidential information will only be stored on a Value4Farm online environment (SharePoint) provided by the project coordinator. This SharePoint is only accessible for the project partners using a password.

Table 1: Data types used in the Value4Farm project

Data type	Data format	Expected file size	Storage
Report Meeting minutes	.docx, .pdf	50 - 500 kB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services Public deliverables: Value4Farm website All deliverables: HORIZON EUROPE F&T portal
Checklist Management templates	.xlsx	50 - 500 kB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services
Presentation	.pptx, .pdf	2 - 20 MB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services Public presentations: Value4Farm website
Questionnaire	.xlsx, .docx, .pdf	500 kB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services
Attendance list	.docx, .pdf	50 - 500 kB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services

Technical processing document	.docx, .xlsx, .csv, .Rdata	50 - 5000 kB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services
Literature references	.enl (Endnote or similar)	50 - 5000 kB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services
Dissemination and Communication material	.zip	5 - 50 MB	Value4Farm website SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services
Picture, image or vector	.jpg, .jpeg, .tiff, .gif, .bmp, .png, .raw and .svg	5 - 20 MB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services Value4Farm website
Template	.docx	500 kB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services
Newsletter	HTML, CSS, .pdf	50 - 5000 kB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services Value4Farm website Mailchimp
Newsletter subscription list	.xlsx	50 - 500 kB	Value4Farm website (back-end) or Mailchimp
Promotional material (brochure, banner, ...)	.pdf, .indd or similar	5 - 50 MB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services Value4Farm website
Scientific publications	.pdf	100 - 1000 kB	SharePoint - Microsoft Online Services Value4Farm website

2.2. WORK PACKAGES

The Project Management Plan is the follow-up tool to manage the project actions, outcomes, and deliverables. It also includes the data necessary to closely monitor the progress of actions and notifies when items are due date. The whole project work plan is broken down into components to ensure a good project management. Every action is attributed to one or more consortium partners.

As this plan includes all actions and responsible partners, an analysis based on what kind of data and data streams will be generated is possible. The responsible partners will ensure that the data will be FAIR, guided by INA as project coordinator.

2.2.1. WP1 – Framework and specifications

Data will be collected in WP1 primarily to inform farmer needs, specifications, and requirements of the demonstration sites. The collection of this data will help to ensure that the crop protocols and energy innovations utilised within the project meet farmer expectations and potential future needs. Data will also be collected related to the demonstration sites, for instance, related to land and soil types and other technical information. Taken together, this data will ensure that the project as a whole is impact and user focused, and that the demonstration and replication sites provide a strong springboard for future energy-related technology uptake.

Data where appropriate will be collected or transferred into Microsoft excel for storage purposes and then uploaded into appropriate software [i.e., “R” or SPSS] for more detailed statistical analysis where necessary. It is likely that existing datasets on soils type and characteristics will be utilised where possible to avoid duplication of effort.

The origin of the farmer-related data will be from questionnaires and focus groups undertaken as part of the WP. Both data collection exercises have been subject to ethical clearance procedures that are in place at the University of Reading. Data cannot be traced back to participating respondents, although is identifiable by Country of origin. All focus group participants have signed a declaration of informed consent.

As well as informing the deliverables as part of WP1 it is hoped that data collected will form the basis for articles in the V4F newsletter, various presentations to farmers and more formal academic publications.

2.2.2. WP2 – Development of the renewable-based crop protocols

WP2 will mainly generate data on innovative microturbines suitable for biogas valorisation, of which some will be IPR protected. This data generation will build on already existing data from other projects and private research. Next to this, data related to the three agricultural protocols and off-grid biomethane plants will be collected. Therefore, a literature review will be done in the three regions, potentially expanded with some experimental results.

The collection of these data will be important for the set-up of the demonstrations (WP3) and the assessment and optimisation of the value chains (WP4). The data will mainly be generated in a report

(.docx or .pdf). The outcomes of the protocols will also be useful for agricultural advisors, as well as farmers. The comprehensive study for off-grid biomethane plants will in the first place be important for other researchers, as well as policy makers.

2.2.3. WP3 – Demonstration of the optimised value chains

WP3 will assess potentials of renewable based energy production systems based on both electricity and biofuels through processing data collected from the demonstration sites. For instance, the Danish system includes three subsystems including (1) agrivoltaics (encompassing vertical and conventional tilted photovoltaic panels), (2) on-site green biorefinery, and (3) biogas reactor (upgrading by thermophilic anaerobic digestion and in-situ biomethanation technology). In agrivoltaics, specified agronomic data will be collected, which mostly circles around crops performance, vegetative indices, and soil and meteorological characteristics. Crops data would be based on a novel rotation underneath or in between the solar panels, which includes wheat as a common trans-European crop and legumes (e.g. blue lupin, grass clover) as nitrogen-fixing crops, and cover crops (e.g. mustard). Within the on-site green biorefinery subsystem, data are around processing of grass clover and cover crops including data on energy consumption and mass balances and flowrates of biomass inputs and value-added product outputs. Also process parameter data such as pressures, temperature and pH can be shared together with product quality data. In the biogas reactor subsystem, collected data mostly relies on process conditions, mass balances and energy efficiency in the overall methane production. Through the synergy of the designed subsystems, it is expected to maximize land-use efficiency by involving agricultural streams (e.g. manure and digestate) for nutrient recycling and reduction of external chemical fertilizers and crop production products. The results of taking these innovative actions will contribute to developing decision making tools and guidelines to accelerate adoption to emerging energy-related technologies.

2.2.4. WP4 – Assessment and optimisation of the value chains

WP4 will collect and generate comprehensive data to meet specific objectives within sustainability assessment. The primary purpose is to assess the environmental, techno-economic, and social aspects of the demonstrated value chains in Denmark, Italy, and Belgium. This includes conducting Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) to evaluate environmental impacts and social life cycle assessment (S-LCA), soil and biodiversity analyses, technico-economic analyses, and social acceptance studies. The data generated will be presented in the form of PDF reports and online materials for the decision support tool (DST). The types of data will vary, including LCA results, financial and economic analyses, soil parameters, biodiversity information, and stakeholder opinions. The size of the data is expected to be substantial, covering various dimensions of the value chains. Existing data will be reused where applicable, leveraging general data initially and refining it based on specific contributions from different stages of the value chains. The data's origin lies in the demonstration sites and relevant methodologies developed within the project. The collected data will be valuable for different stakeholders, including policymakers, agricultural advisors, farmers, researchers, and the general public. The results will contribute not only to decision-making within the project but also to broader discussions on sustainable agricultural practices and renewable energy incorporation.

2.2.5. WP5 – Market uptake of the renewable energy solutions

WP5 will ensure viable uptake and effective replication of the renewable-based solution developed. For each demonstrated value chain, a market analysis will be conducted. Afterwards the group of stakeholders involved will then be trained through field sessions and workshops. Specifically, they will be briefed on legal aspects, best practice, economy of scale, safety, and incentives. In the last phase partners will guide the farms in the next steps to implement the possible value chains and uptake of the demonstrated technologies. Going forward, WP5 will cover background, sideground, and foreground intellectual property rights (IPR) together with a description of rules and practices the consortium will adopt for IPR management, transfer of knowledge and dissemination.

The data will mainly be generated in a report (.docx, .ppt or .pdf).

2.2.6. WP6 – Communication, dissemination and exploitation

WP6 will collect stakeholders' data through the newsletters through MailChimp, through which stakeholders will be able to subscribe with their name and e-mail addresses. The data collected will not be used for other purposes than to send newsletters through MailChimp, and will not be accessible to any other organization apart from EQY, who manages the MailChimp account. Data collected via social media and website will only serve for statistical purposes and are anonymized.

For dissemination and exploitation purposes, the data collected via the communications activities (website, newsletters, events) and partners interactions with their own stakeholders - consisting of names, emails, telephone numbers, job titles and affiliations - will be kept within the WP6 SharePoint platform in password-protected excel files. The data will strictly be used to keep stakeholders - in particular members of the technology providers and end-users boards - aware of progress and to invite them to site visits and meetings. The data will not be shared with parties outside of the Project Consortium partners.

2.2.7. WP7 – Project management and ethics

Project Management derived data facilitate the Value4Farm project partners to keep track on the project progress and efficiently interact with other participants. It mainly comprises of participants contact details (.xlsx), meeting minutes (.docx or .pdf) and presentations (.pptx or .pdf) of about 50-1000 kB. These documents will only be available to the participants on the SharePoint. Hence, these are for internal use only in order to facilitate the project progress.

3. DATA CAPTURING, HANDLING AND MANAGING

3.1. REFERENCES AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

For scientific references, the following reference styles are advised: MLA, APA, Chicago, and Harvard style. The consortium is advised to acknowledge the persons that provided additional information.

Acknowledgements and references should also be cited when applicable in the different dissemination materials elaborated in the project.

Referencing will be managed by using a disclaimer displayed on Value4Farm Website:

These Value4Farm outcomes has been developed only using published material from different open access sources, and have no commercial or comparative purposes. For enquiries on specific items or if you do not agree with the dissemination of the information, please contact us at contact@value4farm.eu.

EQY will manage this mailbox and distribute enquires to the best possible partner in order to fulfil with the requests made.

3.2. DATA SECURITY

Project related data is generally stored on a Microsoft SharePoint which has limited user access: Data access is only possible after logging with an authenticated user and password. Every user is prompted to use a strong password and to regularly follow updates on their personal computer and company servers if any. Anti-virus and firewall programs are advised. SharePoint permissions are managed by INA as Project Coordinator. Deleted files are stored in the bin on Microsoft SharePoint online for 90 days. Afterwards a back-up can be retrieved for maximally 3 years.

Data stored on the website is encrypted and can be accessed only with a dedicated login following the SSL/TLS (https) protocols. Only EQY can access the back-end of the website and the platform. The only data retrieve from the website will be the analytics with number of page visits and users of the website. All data is anonymised.

All data kept into Value4Farm website are daily backed up thanks to the website hosting plan for ensuring the smooth operation. The procedure of restoring the data is totally automated by selecting the date of the backup that will be used for recovery. As well, the data are stored on a EQY cloud account by the web developer.

Participation in surveys is voluntary and can be recalled at any time. The interview will be filed anonymously. When filling the online survey form, the IP address will be identified but not being public and used only for statistical purpose. All final documentation and results of the survey will be in digital form, that will be published in anonymised. Participants for focus groups will have to sign a consent form (ANNEX 2).

3.3. RESOURCE ALLOCATION

Staff efforts for data management and preservation have been included in WP7. Furthermore, INA as coordinator appointed a dedicated Data Protection Officer (DPO), with particular emphasis for the personal data collected. The personal data will be dealt in accordance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national laws, in particular EU Directive 95/46/EC to limit the impact on the persons concerned and ensure data quality and confidentiality. The GDPR 2016/79 is taken into consideration and compliance under its articles will be ensured. All necessary measures to achieve compliance will be undertaken (e.g. consent forms, data protection officer appointment, etc.). After the

end of the project, costs for long-term data preservation will be undertaken by each partner for the data backed-up on their servers.

Data storage costs are within the overhead costs of the consortium partners involved. Storage costs for the Microsoft SharePoint Online environment are covered by INA and not by the project.

Costs related to open access to research data are eligible. Therefore, part of the acquired budget will be attributed to publish scientific articles as open access.

4. MAKING DATA FAIR

This DMP complies with the FAIR principles. Hence, it will guarantee that data are Findable, Accessible Interoperable and Reusable.

4.1. FINDABILITY OF DATA/RESEARCH OUTPUTS

Each partners' institutional repositories will be used to store and back up data collected/generated all along Value4Farm according to their usual practices. The data will be stored in servers physically hosted in EU or EEA countries, to make sure that the EU laws apply. Relevant project data will also be stored on a secure project SharePoint, accessible only by the project participants. Data on the SharePoint will be easily findable via a logical folder structure and a good naming convention. Deliverables will be named DX.X Title (as described in Grant Agreement) (e.g. D7.2 Data Management Plan). All other files stored on SharePoint will be named yymmdd_ document name (e.g. 230908_Minutes Pre KoM). Via 'version history', previous versions of documents can easily be tracked. However, when specific updates are expected (e.g. this DMP), versioning will be specified by version numbers (format Vxx). Small deviations related to this naming convention are allowed after consultation with INA.

Furthermore, data that is not submitted to IPR, as well as outcomes of the project, will mainly be exploited in publications (each with its own digital object identifier (DOI)), in line with open science practices. It will be also available on the project website and social media, as well as stored on a trusted repository (e.g. Zenodo or the European open science cloud), in a standard format abiding by the open research data requirements. Other outputs (e.g. reports) will be searchable via common search engines. In all public output, keywords will be foreseen to facilitate data findability.

Each dataset will be accompanied by metadata to ensure its findability. This metadata still has to be elaborated by the involved partners but can include the title, author, subjects, keywords, publisher, ...

4.2. ACCESSIBILITY OF DATA/RESEARCH OUTPUTS

Using the aforementioned secure project SharePoint, partners will have full access to all relevant collected/generated data. Upon legitimate request, partners may grant specific access to third parties with respective partners' approval. However, it is not expected that third parties will need access to the SharePoint since all public documents will be published already via the project website and social media.

Deliverables and other project outputs which have been annotated as 'Public' will be made openly available by default via the project website, accessible by the visitors through the browser of his choice (Firefox, Chrome, Microsoft Edge etc.) and by navigating to <https://www.value4farm.eu>, as well as via social media. Outputs will be published in conventional formats, accessible via open-source software.

Research data will be published in scientific journals following the Open Access rules. Linking with scientific journals will lead to the creation of Digital DOIs for the specific articles. Raw experimental data will be confidential until they are they are processed into a relevant set of data, ready for publication. The processing and critical review of data is indispensable to ensure the quality of the published data.

IPR protected data will be managed according to the IPR management (T5.3).

4.3. INTEROPERABILITY OF DATA/RESEARCH OUTPUTS

Data will be converted to interoperable formats by using common software packages (e.g., xsl, docx, pdf, etc.) whenever possible, to ensure that each partner can access and process it.

Value4Farm outputs will pay attention to use vocabulary and terminology which is clear and avoids confusion regarding exact meaning and understanding.

4.4. REUSABILITY OF DATA/RESEARCH OUTPUTS

Dissemination/communication material will be open to re-use by third parties as soon as they are made available free of charge on the project website/social media. Furthermore, data will remain usable after the end of Value4Farm to plan ongoing impact, also by interested third parties if referred to properly. This will be possible as the consortium has authorship of re-usable data and documents.

The Value4Farm website will be licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license. This license applies to all contents on the website except where expressly indicated on the page or in the document and except for contents aggregated from other websites, in which case the original licensing applies.

5. GDPR

To respect the GDPR requirements, whenever data subjects are involved in activities such as e.g. questionnaires, a GDPR Tool with flow chart (Figure 2) has been developed to determine which measures need to be taken by the consortium partners to protect the collected data. This tool is available on the Project Sharepoint for all consortium members.

Figure 2: Flowchart of the GDPR-Tool

To inform the data subjects about their rights under the GDPR regulation, a GDPR information sheet has been compiled and is to be given to the data subjects together with an informed consent template. The GDPR information sheet informs about:

- The right to access
- The right to rectification
- The right to erasure

- The right to restrict processing
- The right to object to processing
- The right to data portability

Contact information of DPO's or contact persons for data related issues (for partner organisations that are not required to have a DPO) are also provided to the data subjects.

GDPR information sheet and informed consent templates are provided to the consortium (ANNEX 2).

6. SUPPORT GUIDELINES

6.1. GENERAL VALUE4FARM RECOMMENDATIONS

We recommend to:

- follow the naming conventions outlined in the Data Management Plan;
- use the SharePoint - Microsoft online services to communicate between the consortium and share data;
- make use of common templates for different data types such as deliverables and presentations;
- In case personal data is collected or processed, use the Value4Farm GDPR Tool to determine what measures need to be taken to comply with GDPR
- review and correct the data, even when preventable inadequacies occur;
- to deposit the project's scientific publications to Open Access Journal repository, partners' institutional repository, Value4Farm website and/or Zenodo repository;
- add the appropriate acknowledgements when citing;
- use the open access licensing schema for the publications and reports related to Value4Farm outcomes;
- be aware and acquire informed consent of data subjects involved;
- make use of the EIP-AGRI common format.

6.2. RECOMMENDATIONS TO THE EXECUTIVE BOARDS MEMBERS (WP LEADERS)

We recommend to:

- support the task leaders in the actions that capture, handle and/or generate data for the work package you are leading;
- set-out clear work flows to efficiently undertake the actions needed.

6.3. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE GENERAL ASSEMBLY (ALL PARTICIPANTS)

We recommend to:

- use your network to get relevant data to the consortium for use in the work plan;
- inspire the consortium with examples of good practice.

6.4. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR NETWORK BUILDING

We recommend to:

- Always link to the website in dissemination and/or communication activities.
- Encourage contacts to subscribe to the newsletter

7. CONCLUSION

This DMP summarizes what data (type, size, format) are going to be collected and generated in the different WPs of the Value4Farm project. These data are going to be FAIR, complying with Open Science Practices. A DPO will ensure that personal data will be protected at any time following ethical guidelines. This deliverable is a living document that can be updated every six months, by progressing insights or whenever significant changes arise.

ANNEX I: GENERAL PROCEDURE AND CRITERIA TO IDENTIFY OR RECRUIT RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

The consortium ensures that the research methodologies will not result in discriminatory practices or unfair treatment. Participant selection will be necessary for activities in all work packages.

Involving the end-user in project activities will be based on voluntary action by the end-user. Invitations for activities will be published through the diverse channels of the project and the consortium. Data subjects will be able to register upfront for the activities or will register the day of the activity. At the moment of registration and also at the day of the activity the informed consent templates and information sheet will be given with to the participants for signature. The organizer of the activity shall clarify the items in the information sheet and answer on questions related to it. Special notice will be given to the data subjects rights under the GDPR.

Each member of the project consortium can introduce experts that in his or her opinion can be of added value in attaining the goals set out in the project. Gender equality and inclusiveness will be monitored in detail in order to provide equal opportunities for all gender identities.

ANNEX II: INFORMED CONSENT TEMPLATE

Participants to V4F activities will be informed about the use of their personal data, captured when necessary for the project activity. Informed consent of the participants will be obtained by providing the participants with a document that informs them correctly about the purpose, use and conservation of their personal data.

Therefore a template has been created that, according to the activity and different audiences, will be adapted (see [...] sections) and translated in the native tongues of the participants.

To inform the data subjects about their rights regarding the personal data that they have provided, a GDPR information sheet is also handed over to the data subjects, translated into their native tongue.

TEMPLATE INFORMED CONSENT:

ABOUT THE VALUE4FARM PROJECT: Value4Farm has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research programme under Grant Agreement No 101116076.

The Value4Farm project aims to demonstrate the effectiveness, sustainability and replicability of three renewable-based local value chains coupling sustainable food production and renewable-energy production. This will contribute to the defossilisation of the agricultural sector by matching local needs in terms of electricity, heat, mobility, residual bioresources and land management.

PURPOSE OF YOUR PARTICIPATION: You are invited to participate in [specify activity] framed in the Value4Farm project. The objectives of this activity are [specify activity, for example “gather knowledge on renewable energy needs in agriculture”].

TIME INVOLVEMENT: This activity takes [specify duration] and its result will be published by February 2027 (end of the Value4Farm project).

RISKS AND BENEFITS: The risks associated with this study are negligible. We do not guarantee or promise that you will receive any benefits from this study. Your decision whether or not to participate in this study will not affect your participation in other Value4Farm events and activities.

PAYMENT: You will not receive any reimbursement as payment for your participation.

RIGHTS: If you have read this form and have decided to participate in this research project, please understand that your participation is voluntary and you have the right to withdraw your consent or discontinue participation at any time without penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. The alternative is not to participate. You have the right to refuse to answer particular questions. Your name and contact data will be always retained confidential, and will never be public, findable or accessible.

CONTACT INFORMATION: If you are not satisfied on how this study is being conducted, or have any concerns, complaints, or general questions about the activity or your rights as a participant, please contact [insert the name, e-mail address and phone number of the activity developer / WP leader]:

ALTERNATIVE CONTACT: If you have any questions, concerns or complaints about this research, its procedures, risks and benefits, contact the Data Protection Officer (Anja Lemmens, anja.lemmens@inagro.onmicrosoft.com) of the Project Coordinator (Sofie Declerck, sofie.declerck@inagro.be).

PROCESSING AND PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA: This activity does NOT involve the collection of personal data.

Indicate Yes or No:

- *I give consent to be audiotaped during this study:* ___ Yes ___ No
- *I give consent to be videotaped during this study:* ___ Yes ___ No
- *I give consent for audios and/or videos resulting from this study to be used at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes:* ___ Yes ___ No
- *On default, your identity (name and contact data) will be retained anonymous and confidential, unless you give explicit consent to reveal your identity:* ___ Yes

Name:

SIGNATURE

Place:

Date:

TEMPLATE GDPR INFORMATION SHEET:

You participated in an activity of the Value4Farm project and therefore we needed some personal data to register your participation. Apart from the Informed Consent document you filled out, we wish to emphasise and explain your rights regarding the data you have provided.

Regarding the personal data you shared with us, you have the following rights:

- **The right to access** - You have the right to request the Value4Farm consortium for copies of your personal data.
- **The right to rectification** - You have the right to request that the Value4Farm consortium correct any information you believe is inaccurate. You also have the right to request the Value4Farm consortium to complete the information you believe is incomplete.

- **The right to erasure** - You have the right to request that the Value4Farm consortium erase your personal data, under certain conditions, one of which in so far as this does not threaten or threaten to seriously jeopardize the achievement and validity of the scientific research objectives.
- **The right to restrict processing** - You have the right to request that the Value4Farm consortium restrict the processing of your personal data, under certain conditions, one of which in so far as this does not threaten or threaten to seriously jeopardize the achievement and validity of the scientific research objectives.
- **The right to object to processing** - You have the right to object to project processing of your personal data, under certain conditions.
- **The right to data portability** - You have the right to request that the Value4Farm consortium transfers the data that we have collected to another organization, or directly to you, under certain conditions.

If you want to exercise these rights, please contact the person(s) mentioned on the Informed Consent document.

ANNEX III: LIST OF APPOINTED DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS AND/OR DETAILED DATA PROTECTION POLICY PER BENEFICIARY

The following table gives an overview of the DPO contacts in the consortium:

Table 2: Overview appointed DPO per partner

Participant N°	Short name	DPO contact details
1	INA	Anja Lemmens (Anja.lemmens@inagro.onmicrosoft.com)
2	AU	Peter Severin de Fonss (dpo@au.dk)
3	UCSC	Ferdinando Zanatti (dpo@unicatt.it)
4	WU	Frans Pingen (frans.pingen@wur.nl)
5	UFZ	Nicole Lichtenstein (datenschutz@ufz.de)
6	EIHP	Valent Pessi (zastita.podataka@eihp.hr)
7	IUNG	Julita Grzegórska (julita.grzegorska@iung.pulawy.pl)
8	MITIS	Danish Rehman (danish.rehman@mitis.be)
9	REM	Iliana Le Bossenec (lebossenec@remtec.energy)
10	CIB	Not required
11	OKD	Not required
12	EQY	Nadia Moussaïd (nadia.moussaid@euroquality.fr)
13	UREAD	Robert Dardy (r.m.darby@reading.uk)
14	WBA	Jocelyne Bia (jbia@worldbiogasassociation.org)

For those partners not required to appoint a DPO, a policy on data protection is elaborated, outlined as below. In the Value4Farm consortium these partners are CIB and OKD.

DATA PROTECTION POLICY FOR CIB AND OKD

The partners not required to appoint a DPO engage to follow the data protection principles of the GDPR:

DATA PROTECTION PRINCIPLES

Article 5 of the GDPR requires that personal data shall be:

- a) processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to individuals;

- b) collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes;
- c) adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed;
- d) accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay;
- e) kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed; personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by the GDPR in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of individuals; and
- f) processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures.

DATA SUBJECTS' RIGHTS

Data subjects will be informed about their rights regarding the personal data they've shared so that they understand what their rights are and how they can exercise those rights.

DATA PROCESSING

- The support guidelines in this deliverable will be followed to process data according to the principles of the GDPR.
- A register of systems will be kept, meaning a register of all systems or contexts in which personal data is processed by resp. partners.

DATA RESPONSIBILITY FOR THE VALUE4FARM PROJECT – CONTACT PERSONS:

- **CIB - Consorzio Italiano Biogas**
 Carlo Pieroni
 Employee in the research and development area
 Consorzio Italiano Biogas
 Via A. Einstein snc, Parco Tecnologico Padano

26 900 Lodi (LO), Italy
c.pieroni@consorziobiogas.it
+39 371 466 26 33

- **OKD - Orkidea Samstarfsverkefni**

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